

Design, Manufacture and Test of Graphite Comoposite Wing Box Test Structure

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ABSTRACT

The wing box program presented in this paper is part of an effort at Saab-Scania to evaluate our design and manufacturing ability for wet wing structures made from graphite composite material.

A wing box test structure incorporating a number of critical design features is presented.

Typical data for a high performance light weight fighter aircraft have been used to generate design loads and critical dimensions. The design criteria and structural analysis procedures are discussed.

The manufacturing of the test box is described along with two repair actions that were performed to save expensive subassemblies from scrapping.

Results from static and fatigue tests including the effects from temperature and fuel pressure are presented and compared with analytical predictions. Static loading to failure have for practical reasons been performed at room temperature. The ultimate load prediction is evaluated.

It is concluded that the generally good agreement between analytical predictions and test results reinforce the confidence in our ability to design a wet wing structure in graphite composite material.

INTRODUCTION

The next generation of fighter aircraft, after the Saab 37 family, now under study at Saab-Scania is designed to have a major part of the structure made from graphite epoxy composite material. Although a good number of composite parts already have been successfully introduced on the Saab 37, the new project is a significant development step, particularly with regard to the wing structure.

The objective of the wing box program is to evaluate a number of critical design features on the simplest feasible test structure in order to get an early indication of potential pitfalls and also to evaluate our present design and manufacturing ability with regard to a wet wing structure.

Particularly, design problems related to the following features were studied:

1. Substructure of graphite composite material.
2. Bonded lower cover to substructure assembly.
3. Effect of fuel pressure on cover stability.
4. Bolted on fittings at root joint.

DESIGN

Structural Arrangement

The test article is a rectangular box loaded as a cantilever beam. The loads are applied by two hydraulic jacks at the extremities of the tip rib. In the root end the box is attached to the supporting framework by bolted on steel fittings and tension bolts (Figure 1.).

Substructure. The substructure consists of five spars and an intermediate rib connected by bolted shear clips of T-section. The spars and intermediate rib have a symmetric I-section and have constant height.

At each end the box is closed by flush fitting steel ribs. The spar webs are attached to the root and tip rib by bolted T-section shear clips. The root rib is bolted to the supporting frame. The tip rib is attached to the covers by bolted steel angles. The tip rib is provided with holes for pressurization of the box.

The entire substructure except the closing ribs is made from graphite/epoxy tape material.

Covers. Basically each cover is a continuous 20-ply laminate extending over the entire box surface. In the fitting area the covers are thickened by additional plies interspersed in the basic laminate. A number of these plies are extended in the spanwise direction at the spar locations to form integral spar caps.

The lower cover is bonded to the substructure using BSL308A film adhesive. The upper cover is bolted to the substructure using countersunk fasteners and plate nuts. In order to keep costs within available funds it was decided to turn the covers upside down giving a flat faying surface between the covers and substructure thus considerably simplifying the tooling.

Attachment fittings. Cover loads are transferred to the steel fittings by 48 steel bolts arranged in three rows and sixteen columns. Five pairs of tension bolts then transfer the axial loads to the supporting frame.

Design criteria

Design criteria representative of a real fighter wing structure was chosen as far as feasible. Thus, such features as damage tolerance, durability and repairability is included in the design considerations although no specific actions were taken to explore the limits of the structure in that respect.

Environment. All design allowables have been chosen with regard to a continuous operating temperature of +70°C and a maximum and minimum operating temperature of +100°C and -50°C respectively. Allowance is made for 1% moisture content in the laminates.

Damage tolerance. The composite structure is required to be able to sustain a damage equivalent to a 6 mm diameter hole in any arbitrary part up to D.U.L..

Durability. The composite structure is required to sustain 2 lifetimes of spectrum fatigue loading and to have a residual static strength not less than

D.U.L. (Design Ultimate Load). As we don't yet have any analytical means of predicting damage growth and residual strength, the durability requirement is assumed to be satisfied by the following criteria.

1. The laminates shall be free from matrix cracking up to 1.15 D.L.L. (Design Limit Load).
2. Buckling must not occur below 1.15 D.L.L..

Safety factor. Static failure must not occur below 1.5 D.L.L..

Design loads

The box is loaded by external forces and internal pressure. Three static load cases were considered for stressing the structure.

- a) Bending up and down.
- b) Torsion.
- c) Internal pressure.

The actual loads for these cases are given in table 1.

Detail Design

The [0/90/+45] family of laminates with a balanced layup have been used throughout the box according to the present Saab-Scania design philosophy. Ply orientation was optimized with regard to the loading of each structural element and strength margins checked for critical load conditions using standard Saab-Scania Structural Manual procedures.

"Far field" strength margins are based on the "max strain" failure criterion. Evaluation of the design criteria resulted in an allowable fibre strain of 4300 microstrain in tension and compression.

For the lower cover spar caps it was decided, however, to depart from the manual. Because of the tension dominated spectrum, damage growth was judged to be less critical and the tension allowable was raised to 5200 microstrain.

Load distribution. Internal loads were obtained from an ASKA finite element analysis. The cover panels as well as the spar and rib webs were modelled with anisotropic QUAM8 elements while FLA3 bar elements were used to model the spar caps. The root attachment area was analyzed in detail by a hand balance procedure for the critical bending case.

Cover panels. The cover panels are designed to resist the shear from torsional loads and to transfer the pressure loads to the spars and ribs. Optimization of the panels with regard to flexural stiffness and buckling resulted in a [0/8/12] laminate with flexural stiffness due to surface weaviness restrictions as the critical condition.

Stability analysis predicted buckling to start at 187 percent D.L.L. for the critical torsion case.

Spar caps. The spar caps are designed to resist the bending forces and are tapered in the spanwise direction to match the bending moment distribution. Each spar cap consists of a constant section spar flange and a tapered integral cap in the cover (figure 2).

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The additional axial stiffness required to carry the cap loads for the

bending case was obtained by putting unidirectional plies in the cover. In the upper cover the required stiffness derived from the fiber strain criteria was increased by 8% to allow for the bolt loads.

Spar webs. All spar webs are basically the same [4/6/16] laminate optimized with regard to shear buckling and bolted joint strength for the loading in the root area. Outboard of the fittings however, part of the laminate is replaced by a 2 mm aluminum honeycomb core leaving a [0/1/4] skin on each side. This web being optimized for buckling strength and foundation stiffness in the bending case. Analysis showed positive margins for all loading cases for the intermediate spars while the front and rear spar had negative margins in buckling for the torsion case. Buckling strength was increased by adding bolted on T-section stiffeners. Repeated analysis showed zero fiber strength margin in the panels between stiffeners for the torsion case. In all bolted joint areas the solid [4/6/16] web was left intact for bearing strength reasons.

Attachment area. In the attachment area the covers are optimized for bolted joint strength resulting in a [32/8/24] and a [26/8/20] laminate in the upper and lower cover respectively. The different thicknesses reflects the difference in tension and compression allowables.

The kick loads on the fittings are balanced by connecting the outboard and inboard end of the fittings to the substructure (figure 3). Outboard, aluminum fittings are used to transfer the loads into the webs at each spar location. Inboard the fitting is bolted to the closure rib with the tension bolts passing through clearance holes.

MANUFACTURE

Material

All composite parts were manufactured from Fiberite HyE 1034E graphite epoxy tape material and were processed according to Saab-Scania specification FiA 14:12

Substructure

The spars, the intermediate rib, the T-section stiffeners and shear clips were all manufactured on the same type of aluminum tool.

The spars were manufactured as a cocured assembly of two channel sections, a web plate and two flange caps. The separate parts were laid flat ply by ply using mylar templates. The channel sections then were shaped by wrapping the laminates over the each tool half using a hair dryer to form the radius. The web plate was laid on one of the tool halves and aluminum core placed in the cut out areas. Finally the tool halves were assembled back to back and the corners at the flange radius were filled with EA 9601 rope adhesive. The flange caps were laid on and held in place by aluminum pressure plates.

The whole assembly was autoclave cured at 175°C. The core bonding was performed by excessive resin flowing into the core during the cure cycle.

Covers. The covers were laid ply by ply on a flat aluminum tool using mylar templates. Standard bagging and autoclave cure procedure were used.

Assembly

Assembly of the box was made in two major operations. First the spars and intermediate rib was bonded to the lower cover. Secondly, all mechanically fastened parts were assembled.

Bonding. Bonding was performed in a hot press. A fibreglass pressure plate was fabricated using the lower cover as a mold. When placed in the press the upper surface of the cover formed a flat, evenly supported surface parallel to the press table. The spars and ribs were placed on the cover and were properly fixed by tooling pins and clamps. As the spar and rib webs were too flexible to support the bonding pressure, aluminum honeycomb core blocks were inserted

between the flanges thus effectively transferring the pressure to the lower flange surfaces. The pressure distribution was checked by making a number of dry runs with a thick sheet of paper between the upper press plate and the box. The core blocks were adjusted by sanding until the dry run showed a uniform indentation from the flanges in the paper sheet. A final checkout was made with a blind bonding operation, where the adhesive film was separated from the faying surfaces by thin mylar sheets. After curing, the mylar sheets were removed and the thickness of the bondline between the sheets was measured with a micrometer. By further adjusting the core blocks and using twin adhesive films in some areas a good quality bondline was achieved after a second blind bonding operation.

Final assembly. All mechanically fastened parts were installed after the bonding operation. Around the periphery of the box all parts were faying surface sealed and the fasteners were wet installed. Before the upper cover was attached the interior of the box was painted with epoxy varnish. In the next step the root attachment fittings were bolted to the covers. To achieve a perfect faying surface the fittings were set in a layer of room temperature curing, Aerobond liquid shim paste. After curing of the shim the bolts were properly torqued. Before closing the box additional sealant was applied on the box interior at bolts and gaps. Finally the root and tip rib was installed and sealed.

Repairs

During the assembly of the box two deviations from the drawings were reported. In the first case a tooling error resulted in that 250 holes in the upper cover were countersunk far too deep. The cover was saved from scrapping by bonding aluminum bushings into the holes and then make the correct countersinking in the bushing (figure 4). In the second case a shear clip connecting the front spar and intermediate rib was misplaced resulting in that fastener holes were drilled in the unreinforced part of the web. As the damage tolerance criteria requires that the design allowables must include allowance for the effect of a 6 mm hole, the repair action was simply to plug the holes with fasteners and drill new holes in the proper places.

TESTING

Test Equipment

The test set up is shown in figure 5. Internal pressure and temperature was provided by circulating heated water through the box. Pressure was controlled by a servovalve on the outlet side.

Test Procedure

After a number of preliminary static tests to check out the equipment the following main program was run:

1. Static bending and torsion to D.L.L. Displacement and strain measurements.
2. 6 000 simulated flight hours (2 lifetimes) of fatigue with bending moment spectrum at 60 kPa internal pressure and +70°C temperature.
3. Static bending and torsion to 1.8 D.L.L.. Displacement and strain measurements.
4. Pulsating pressure from 30 kPa to 150 kPa for 200 000 cycles at +70°C. Static pressure loading to 200 kPa.
5. Static loading in torsion to failure at RT without pressure.

Test Results

The preliminary static tests revealed that temperatures up to +70°C and pressures up to 60 kPa did not change the overall bending and torsional stiffness.

No external damage was evident from visual inspection before the failure test. The fatigue loading did not change the bending and torsional stiffness of the box, indicating that no major internal damage had occurred.

The first cracking during the failure test was audible at 200 percent D.L.L.. Thereafter a nonlinear load displacement relationship was observed and final failure occurred at 247 percent D.L.L.. No buckling was observed.

Failure was initiated in the front spar web at the plugged holes (figure 6). The shear failure of the web was followed by delamination of the spar flange along the entire span. The delamination occurred in the laminate leaving the bondline apparently intact. No significant damage was found on the covers or in bolted joint assemblies.

Comparison with Analysis

Stiffness and strains. The tip rib displacement relative to the outboard end of the root fitting at the front and rear spar was calculated from test data and F.E.A. data. Figure 7a show the results plotted versus load for the bending and torsion case.

The spar cap strains from test and F.E.A. results at D.U.L. load for the bending case are shown in figure 7b. The shear strain in the cover and spar webs from tests and F.E.A. results plotted vs. load for the torsion case are shown in figure 7c. Good agreement between test and analysis was obtained in all cases.

Failure load. As discussed earlier such considerations as environmental effects, damage tolerance and durability results in fibre strain allowables considerably below the actual breaking strain of the fibre. Thus the failure load for the box when tested in room temperature under laboratory conditions should be sufficiently over the D.U.L. to make proper allowance for these effects. In the present case failure was initiated at 1.33 D.U.L. and catastrophic failure occurred at 1.65 D.U.L.. From previous experience it is judged that the box showed sufficient margin to ensure structural integrity also for realistic service conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

From the wing box program it is concluded that the basic design and manufacturing procedures for advanced composite structures available at Saab-Scania are relevant and can be successfully applied on a wet wing structure. It is fully understood however that a real structure is significantly more complex, presenting a large number of difficult design problems that have not been studied in this program.

For those problem areas that were studied, good results were obtained which reinforce our confidence in the continued development work on wet wing structures made of graphite composite material.

Figure 1. General arrangement of box.

Load case	P_1 kN	P_2 kN	p kPa
Bending up	41.5	41.5	60
down	-14	-14	60
Torsion	61.7	-61.7	60
Internal pressure	-	-	150

Table 1. Design loads

Figure 3. Fitting detail

Figure 2. Spar cap

Figure 4. Hole repair

Figure 5. Test set up

Figure 6. Failed web

Figure 7. Comparison between test results and analysis.
 a) Displacements vs. load, b) Spar cap strains at D.U.L.,
 c) Shear strain in front and rear spar and cover panel vs. load.